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Research Article

**INVESTIGATION OF DENTAL STATUS AMONG CHILDREN
WITH DISABILITIES**¹Svetlana Gazhva, ²Ekaterina Belousova, ³Elena Zueva¹Doctor of Medicine, Professor, Head of Chair of Dentistry, GBOU VPO "Nizhny Novgorod State Medical Academy, Ministry of Public Health"- stomfpkv@mail.ru²Postgraduate student, Chair of Dentistry, GBOU VPO "Nizhny Novgorod State Medical Academy, Ministry of Public Health"- catpir312@mail.ru³Senior Teacher, Department of Humanities, National Research University Higher School of Economics, Nizhny Novgorod branch - eefremova@hse.ru**Abstract:**

Prevalence of oral diseases among children is an urgent problem that poses a threat to the health of the growing population in Russia. Dental pathology among children with disabilities has specific characteristics regarding its development, prevalence and intensity of the lesion. Statistically, dental morbidity of children with disabilities is much higher than in somatically healthy. This is due to a number of factors: a slowdown in the perception rate, underdevelopment of the cognitive sphere, violation of behavioral reactions and, as a consequence, inadequate compliance with necessary hygienic procedures. The authors consider that the major etiological factor resulting in the development of diseases of oral mucosa and periodontal condition in patients with neuropsychiatric pathology is absence or poor hygienic care of the oral cavity. The aim of the study is to assess the dental status of children with disabilities and autism spectrum disorders aged 3 – 8 years old. To determine this status, the method of defining and calculating indices reflecting the state of oral tissues was employed. The following indexes were used in the study: Fedorov-Volodkina hygienic index; simplified index of oral hygiene (OHI-S/GAMES-Y); papillary-marginal-alveolar index (PMA); Index of tooth decay kp, KPU+kp. Dental examination revealed a high prevalence of dental diseases in children with ASD and cerebral palsy; in particular, multiple lesions of hard tissues of the teeth, periodontal inflammation were identified. The findings of the study showed that caries in children with limited abilities is mainly due to their low motivation to develop a habit of individual manual teeth brushing ritual.

Key words: Dental status, autism spectrum disorder, cerebral palsy, dental caries, gingivitis, poor oral hygiene.

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1. INTRODUCTION:

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), there are 516 million people with disabilities in the world, which constitutes 10% of the total population. Statistics of childhood disability demonstrates its steady growth over the last 10 years from 43.1 per 10,000 children aged 0 to 15 to 196.3 per 10 000 children. (Aliamovskii V. et al. 2015).

In regard to the causes of disability, the first place belongs to diseases of the nervous system (38.3%), the second is taken by the defects of the musculoskeletal system (21.1%). These diseases are likely to result in severe disability since early childhood. Their high incidence rate and steady growth present great challenges in health care of such children. (Škrinjaric T. et al. 2016).

Various diseases refer to permanent disturbances of the central nervous system (CNS), in particular, infantile cerebral palsy. This is known to be one of urgent medical and sociological problems, since this pathology is widespread in the modern world, with its prevalence being 5-6 per 1000 newborns (0.5-0.6%). Diagnostics, prevention and treatment of dental diseases among children and adolescents with disabilities present a significant problem considering difficulties with delivering them dental care due to the severity of clinical manifestations of the underlying disease. (Gazhva S.I. 2018).

The key factor contributing to high intensity and prevalence of dental diseases among children with disabilities is the inability to perform rational manual oral hygiene skills. (Tarasova N.V. et al. 2015). Impaired mobility and coordination of movements in patients with musculoskeletal disorders, difficulties in concentrating attention in individuals with mental retardation and developmental delay, as well as possible behavioral problems in children with mental disorders exclude the possibility of long-term procedures and the use of traumatic medical instruments. (Aliamovskii V. et al. 2015). All of the above contributes to excessive anxiety of the child, along with this complicating and prolonging the performance of dental therapeutic manipulations. Therefore, the main methods to be applied for oral sanitation in children with disabilities are primarily general anesthesia methods. (Stosh V. I. et al 2005).

The major aim of this study is to investigate the need for oral diseases treatment and dental status among children with disabilities.

In order to achieve the aim of the study, the following research questions are addressed:

1. To determine the need for dental rehabilitation for children with disabilities

based on the retrospective analysis of medical records.

2. To study the dental status of children with disabilities.

The study provides an important opportunity to advance the understanding of the problems linked with health care and dental services confronted by children with disabilities. These challenges are becoming increasingly relevant due to the fact that currently the growing number of children with disabilities is concerned about the questions of medical service aimed at health preservation and promotion. Dental health is an integral part of the overall human health. Thus, the state of the oral cavity has a direct impact not only on physical but also on socio-psychological functioning of a human being.

Available literature sources report significantly higher dental morbidity rates among children with disabilities in comparison with the ones among somatically healthy children. This is due to a number of factors: a slowdown in the pace of perception, underdevelopment of the cognitive sphere, violation of behavioral reactions and, as a result, inadequate compliance with the necessary hygienic procedures. This factor is directly related to high prevalence and intensity of the cariosity. When analyzing the causes for the diseases of the tunica mucosa of mouth and periodontal condition in patients with neuropsychiatric pathology, some authors emphasize the absence or deterioration of hygienic oral care as the predominant etiological factor in contrast to severity and duration of the underlying disease. Also, it is worth noting that the impact of using specific medicine is not always taken into account. In a number of publications it is noted that even with sufficient oral hygiene and a short prescription of somatic pathology, dental caries and periodontal disease are more common among patients with disabilities than among healthy people.

The data for the study were collected from 1.468 dental patients' records.

Inclusion criteria included children with disabilities of both sexes between the ages of 3 and 8 years. Of the initial cohort of 74 children, 30 children had autism spectrum disorders and 44 children were diagnosed with cerebral palsy. The overall structure of the study takes the form of two parts:

Stage 1 involved a retrospective analysis of medical records of a dental patient.

At stage 2 a comprehensive dental examination of children with disabilities was carried out.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1 Ethical approval

The project received approval from the Local Ethics Committee of the Federal Publicly Funded Higher Education Institution Privolzhsky Research Medical University of Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation (extract of record No. 22 of 21.12.2017). Written informed consent was obtained from each patient. All participants received oral and written information about the study objectives. The investigation was carried out from September 2017 to September 2018.

2.2 Methods:

It was decided that the best approach to adopt for this investigation is to employ a comparative, randomized, controlled clinical trial with elements of retrospective analysis aimed at studying the dental status in children with disabilities. The most minimally invasive painless and informative methods were applied for the study. They are as follows:

1. The standard method used to determine the dental status is the *visual method*. This approach is traditionally applied to examine the external (extraoral and perioral) and oral cavity (intraoral). The WHO guidelines are taken into account during visual examinations. In compliance with them, different types of examination focus on various aspects. Thus, the extraoral examination assesses the skin color and configuration of the face; the perioral examination checks nasolabial folds and the area of the lips; the intraoral examination is conducted in accordance with the anatomical topographic areas (cheeks (right, left), then the area of the oropharynx (soft and hard palate), palatal surface of the gums on the upper jaw, the tongue, the floor of the mouth, lingual surface of gum on the lower jaw, the entrance to the mouth) - the color of the mucosa (red, white, brown, purple), change of terrain (bubbles, elevation, papules, plaques, vegetation), violation of the integrity (erosion, aphthae, ulcers, cracks), the location, size, number, depth of the lesions being indicated; and, finally,- the state of the mucous glands (derivatives of the epithelium).
2. The *manual method* is one of more practical approaches to palpation of regional lymph nodes (submandibular, chin, neck), paying attention to their size, consistency, tenderness, mobility, adhesion to the underlying tissues in that it is effective to determine the consistency of oral mucosa in the affected areas.
3. The *instrumental method* includes examination of the oral cavity using a dental mirror, a tooth broach and forceps: periodontal probing and percussing on the teeth. Traditionally, determination and calculation of indices reflecting the state of oral tissues offers the most effective way to determine the status of dental health. A major problem with oral hygiene indices is the fact

that despite their diversity, not all of them give an accurate idea of the presence, severity and distribution of plaque. In addition, not all indices used today can be informative in determining the effectiveness of various means and methods of individual oral hygiene. This problem presents a dilemma for every practitioner and researcher.

In order to obtain a true picture of the dental status of all children, the mouth cavity indices evaluation method was used. The following *indices* were selected:

- *Fedorov-Volodkina Hygienic index used for children from 3 to 6 years*. To determine the index, the vestibular surface of the six central lower teeth is examined. These teeth are stained with special solutions (Schiller-Pisarev, fuchsin, erythrosine) and the presence of plaque is evaluated assigning codes by the following criteria: 1 - no plaque detected; 2 - staining one quarter of the tooth crown surface; 3 - staining half the surface of the tooth crown; 4 - staining three quarters of the surface of the tooth crown; 5 - staining the entire surface of the tooth crown. Then, in order to estimate the plaque present in this patient, the obtained codes for each examined stained tooth are added, the total sum divided by 6 afterwards. The only limitation for applying this index is the age (6 years).
- *Simplified index of oral hygiene (OHI-S/GAMES-Y), J. C. Green, J. R. Vermillion (1964)*. To determine the index, 6 teeth are examined (16, 11, 26, 31, 36, and 46). The presence of plaque and calculus on the vestibular surfaces of the 16th, 11th, 26th, 31st teeth is assessed and on lingual surfaces of the 36th and 46th teeth either visually or using a staining solution (Schiller-Pisarev, Magenta, erythrosine). Plaque is estimated using plaque evaluation codes where 0 refers to no plaque detected, 1 identifies soft plaque covering not more than 1/3 of the tooth surface or the presence of any number of painted sediments (green, brown, etc.), 2 indicates soft plaque covering more than 1/3 but less than 2/3 of the tooth surface, 3 means soft plaque covering more than 2/3 of the tooth surface. Similarly, calculus is estimated as follows: 0 - calculus is not revealed; 1 - supragingival calculus covering not more than 1/3 of tooth surface; 2 - supragingival calculus covering more than 1/3 but less than 2/3 of the tooth surface or the presence of separate deposits of subgingival calculus in the cervical area of the tooth; 3 - supragingival calculus covering more than 2/3 of the tooth surface, or significant deposits of subgingival calculus around the cervical area of the tooth). The estimations being conducted, both components are summed for each

evaluated surface; the received sums are add up and divided by the number of examined surfaces. The index is regarded informative only if the child has fully erupted dental crowns in the oral cavity to be examined.

- *Papillary-marginal-alveolar index (PMA)* allows assessing the extent and severity of gingivitis. The number of examined teeth in the integrity of the dentition depends on the age of the subject: 6-11 years – 24 teeth; 12-14 years – 28 teeth; 15 years and older – 30 teeth. Evaluation of the inflammatory process in each tooth is carried out follows: 1 - inflammation of the papilla; 2 - inflammation of the gingival margin; 3 - inflammation of the alveolar gum. The index is calculated by the following formula: $PMA = S \times 100 / 3 \times N$, where S is the sum of the indicators in points, N is the number of teeth examined. The value of the index with a limited prevalence of the pathological process reaches 25%; with the acute prevalence and intensity of the pathological process, the indicators approach 50%, and with the further spread of the pathological process and an increase in its severity – from 51 % or more. The index of tooth decay is defined by the quantitative values of the $KPU = K + P + U$, where K is the number of decayed (untreated) teeth, P –the number filled (treated) teeth, U is the number of extracted teeth or roots of the teeth to be removed, while "KP" index of the teeth was calculated as the sum of carious and sealed temporary teeth.

4. Caries activity was determined by the *method proposed by T. F. Vinogradova*. The method consists in referring the examined patients to the compensated, subcompensated or decompensated form of the course of dental caries, considering caries intensity. Tooth decay takes place with a different activity. At the first degree of activity – compensated – the intensity index does not exceed the average caries index of the corresponding age group living in the given area. At the second degree of activity- subcompensated –the caries index is above the average intensity value for the relevant age group. For the third degree of activity – decompensated –caries intensity exceeds the maximum indicator for this age group.

5. *Statistical method*. The obtained results of the conducted clinical and laboratory studies were subjected to statistical analysis using Statistical Program Package Microsoft Office® 365 (Microsoft Corporation, Seattle, USA), Microsoft Excel and the statistical package STADIA V8.

The study was conducted on the basis of the LLC Nizhny Novgorod branch of the clinic "Sadko" and

the Chair of Dentistry in the Federal Publically Funded Higher Education Institution Privolzhsky Research Medical University.

The study was a prolonged investigation carried out over the period of 12 months.

The distributions of the studied features to the proximity to the normal distribution (Gauss distribution) were analyzed.

The analysis revealed that the distributions of most samples are different from the normal one. Therefore the comparison was performed using nonparametric methods of statistics (medians were compared): for unpaired samples Wilcoxon and Van der Waerden test was applied, whereas for paired samples – Wilcoxon test (for paired samples) and Signed-Rank test. When sample distributions were nearly normal, comparison was performed using Student's t-test (mean values were compared).

2.3. Material or Data collection

To determine the need for dental care for children with cerebral palsy and autism spectrum disorders, a total of 468 dental charts were investigated for the study. All the charts of the reporting form were taken from the Nizhny Novgorod Department of the JSCB Sadko clinic (Russia) covering the period of 2016 - 2018.

The following indicators were analyzed:

1. Total number of admitted children with cerebral palsy and autism spectrum disorders;
2. Number of patients in need of orthodontic treatment;
3. Number of patients in need of therapeutic treatment;
4. Number of patients in need of surgical treatment;
5. Number of admitted patients in need of periodontal disease treatment;
6. Number of admitted patients in need of mucous tunic of the mouth treatment.

This was a dental epidemic instrumental examination of 74 children aged 3 to 8 years. Participants were divided into groups depending on the general somatic pathology. The diagnosis was made based on the opinion of the doctor, the neurologist and the child psychiatrist.

Group 1 included 44 children of both sexes between the ages of 3 to 8 years with cerebral palsy.

In group 2 there were 30 children of both sexes between the ages of 3 to 8 years who had autism spectrum disorders.

Inclusion criteria included both male and female patients aged from 3 to 8, availability of somatic pathology medical history of cerebral palsy, autism

spectrum disorders, presence of informed parental consent to participate in the study and to obtain sanitation of the oral cavity. The exclusion criteria included children with an age range younger than 3 years and older than 8 years, somatically healthy children. Besides, those who refused to further participate in the study or violated the study protocol were excluded from the investigation.

3. RESULTS:

The present study designated to explore the dental status in children with ASD and cerebral palsy detected a combination of several independent types of dental pathology (carious lesions of the

teeth and inflammatory periodontal disease) in this category of children. High prevalence and intensity of diseases of the dental system are mutually aggravated by the course of each other against the background of poor oral hygiene. The following conclusions can be drawn from the present study:

1. The data obtained from retrospective analysis of medical records indicate a high need in the provision of qualified therapeutic dental care for children with autism spectrum disorders (ASD) and cerebral palsy. Moreover, the research findings highlighted the need for organization of expanded preventive work among children with disabilities (Table 1).

Table1: Need in dental care for children with autism spectrum disorders (ASD) and cerebral palsy on the basis of medical documentation (absolute number and percentage).

	Dental activity	Absolute number of dental charts	%
Hygienist	Professional oral hygiene	468	100
Dental therapist	Treatment of dental caries and its complications	433	88
	Treatment of periodontal disease	171	38
	Treatment of mucous tunic of mouth and lips diseases	165	37
Maxillo-facial surgeon	Removal of primary teeth	257	56
Orthodontist	Orthodontic care	45	17
Total	Dental treatment	433	100

3. A comparative randomized controlled study was conducted, which allowed us to analyze the results and draw conclusions. Groups of patients are standardized by age, sex, which gives ground to consider the results comparable. The results of the study indicate that the hygienic index of Fedorov-Volodkina and Green-Vermillion in children with disabilities was mostly unsatisfactory ($p < 0.001$). The worst average indicator of oral hygiene was found in children with cerebral palsy, which amounted to $2.59 \pm 0,02$ points, thus, pointing to an unsatisfactory hygienic condition (Table 2).

Table 2: Comparative assessment of hygiene indices in children

Age	Children with autism spectrum disorders		Children with cerebral palsy	
	Fedorov-Volodkina index	Green-Vermillion index	Fedorov-Volodkina index	Green-Vermillion index
3-5 years	1,4±0,02		1,8±0,02	
6-8 years		2,2±0,02		2,59±0,02

When examining periodontal tissues, children of the first and second groups mainly complained about bleeding gums when brushing teeth and eating, bad breath, dry lips and oral mucosa. A possible explanation for this is that clinical manifestations of periodontal disease in children with cerebral palsy and autism spectrum disorders were more marked due to poor oral hygiene resulting from impaired motor and speech activity.

Another important finding was that the severity of gingivitis according to the papillary marginal alveolar (PMA) index in the group of children with cerebral palsy and autism spectrum disorders corresponded to moderate severity, the PMA index in healthy children of mild severity (0.14 ± 0.08), ($P < 0.05$).

The severity of gingivitis according to the PMA index in the group of children with cerebral palsy and autism spectrum disorders corresponded to moderate severity, the PMA index in healthy children of mild severity constituted (0.14 ± 0.08), ($P < 0.05$). The obtained results demonstrate that the prevalence of caries among children reaches 80%, with intact teeth remaining in 20% of children (Figure 1).

Fig. 1 Prevalence of dental caries in children with ASD

Fig. 2 Prevalence of dental caries in children with cerebral palsy

The findings observed in the study provided ground to determine a significant prevalence and high intensity of caries lesions of milk teeth in groups with ASD and cerebral palsy.

In the overall structure of caries intensity in children aged 3-8 component "K" (number of caries teeth per person) accounts for $82 \pm 3.21\%$, with a predominant injury of primary front dentition and molars. The share of component "p" (number of fillings per person) constitutes $18 \pm 2.87\%$ (Figure 3, Figure 4).

Fig. 3 Tooth decay in the 51st, 52d, 61st, 62d teeth in a child with ASD.

Fig. 4 Tooth decay in the 51st, 52d, 61st, 62d teeth in a child with cerebral palsy.

No removed permanent teeth were identified in the structure of the KPU+kp index. The results of the survey allowed us to determine significant prevalence of dental caries associated with a high intensity of caries lesions in milk teeth. It is revealing that untreated teeth prevail over filled ones in the structure of the KPU+kp index: 64% in contrast to 88%. In addition, 6 affected by caries teeth decay were identified per one child. Of the overall cohort of examined participants, 76% had a compensated form of caries, 18% were diagnosed with a subcompensated form and in 5% of the examined a decompensated form was identified (Figure 5).

Fig. 5 Caries activity in children with ASD and cerebral palsy.

4. CONCLUSION:

The findings observed in this study mirror those of the previous investigations that have underlined the importance of dental treatment for children with limited abilities living in the territory of the Russian Federation. The results of retrospective analysis of medical records identified a high need in the provision of qualified therapeutic dental care for children with ASD and cerebral palsy. Besides, necessity in the organization of extended preventive work among children of this contingent was revealed. Another important finding was that a comprehensive dental examination revealed that

children with cerebral palsy and autism spectrum disorder have high prevalence and intensity of caries and low oral hygiene.

The obtained data has been able to demonstrate 100% need for dental care for children with disabilities. Thus, 100% of patients required professional oral hygiene and therapeutic sanitation. The need for surgical treatment for the removal of milk teeth was revealed in 56% of patients. Orthodontic care was provided to 17%.

During the study it was established that the dental status of children with disabilities possesses some features and can therefore be characterized by high prevalence and intensity of the carious process, presence of untreated foci of odontogenic infection, unjustified removal of a large number of teeth, presence of inflammatory phenomena in periodontal tissues, poor oral hygiene affected by high need for treatment of dental diseases.

One of the most significant findings to emerge from this study is that the level of dental health in children with disabilities, unfortunately, still remains an unresolved problem. This is to a large extent due to minimized dental interventions they are exposed to, for objective reasons. Furthermore, residency training is little focused on this category of patients. This can be explained not only by organizational moments in routing and rendering dental care, but also by low motivational potential displayed by this category of children; in particular, their low motivation to learn and apply manual skills of self-service and oral cavity hygiene. In addition, the investigated category of patients have sensory disorders linked with hypersensitivity to the bristles of the toothbrush and intolerance to the taste of toothpaste or tooth powder, which causes children to avoid brushing their teeth, contributing to overall poor oral hygiene. The results of the study indicate a high need in the provision of qualified dental care for children with disabilities. Taken together, these findings support strong recommendations to enhance the effectiveness of dental treatment and prevention measures for children with disabilities. A reasonable approach to tackle this issue could be to implement an interdisciplinary treat principle and develop algorithms for medical examination and rehabilitation of children with disabilities.

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